

Phenyl-Copper(I) as Synthetic Reagent

O. P. Vig, S. D. Sharma and J. C. Kapur

In our earlier communication¹, we have reported the utility of vinyl-copper(I) as synthetic reagent, indicating therein that the reagent provides a simple method for the replacement of a halogen atom in a wide variety of substrates by a vinyl or substituted vinyl group which are hitherto accessible only by lengthy or complicated routes.

In continuation of this work, we wish to communicate that phenyl-copper(I) also behaves in a similar fashion. Analogous to vinyl-copper(I) which has been represented as $\text{Li}^+ \left(\begin{array}{c} | \\ \text{C} \\ / \quad \backslash \\ \text{R} \quad \text{CH}_2 \end{array} \right)_2 \text{Cu}^-$, the phenyl-copper can be assigned the

structure $\text{Li}^+ \left(\times \text{---} \begin{array}{c} \text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \\ \text{---} \end{array} \right)_2 \text{Cu}^-$. The reagent was prepared by the reaction

of phenyl lithium in dry tetrahydrofuran solution with anhydrous cuprous iodide in the molar ratio of 2 : 1 below 0° in an inert atmosphere. The reagent, thus generated, reacts with a number of organic halides and most of the reactions were carried over with 5 moles of the reagent per mole of the halide derivative.

The following chart depicts some of the conversions which have been effected with lithium diphenyl copper.

1. O. P. Vig, J. C. Kapur and S. D. Sharma; *This Journal* (in press).

The products were fractionated under reduced pressure, chromatographed over alumina and characterised through the comparison of their analytical data with the previous synthetic samples or as reported in literature.^{1,2}

The above mentioned synthetic pathway is quite useful in the preparation of unsymmetrically substituted biphenyls, diphenyl methanes, benzophenones etc. which are not accessible through Wurtz' reaction. The reaction can also be utilised for the syntheses of many natural occurring compounds especially the terpenic compounds having phenyl group as part of their structure.

A detailed study of this work is in hand and will be communicated in future. One of the authors is thankful to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a Junior Research Scholarship to one of them (J.C.K.).

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
PANJAB UNIVERSITY,
CHANDIGARH-14.

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